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Welcome to our July 2021 newsletter

In this edition we bring you news of our Summer School 2021 - online and self-paced 6th September to 5th November. Registration is now open so be sure to read on and sign up! There have been further Data Stewardship events and the South Africa School, after 10 weeks, comes to an end very soon, on 9th July. Our alumni being profiled in this edition are Jacqueline Stephens and Neema Simon Sumari and our instructor profile is Venkat Shanmugasundaram. If you're interested in participating at the 3rd webinar in the alumni webinar series taking place 22nd July 2021 - SARS-CoV-2 genomics and data analysis in the UK with Dr Matthew Bashton - read to the end for further details and registration!

2021 Research Data Science Summer School 6 September - 5 November 2021

An ICTP Virtual Meeting, Trieste, Italy

Registration is open for this year's Summer School, providing Early Career Researchers (at MSc-level to 3 years post PhD) and Professionals (registering via ITU Academy) with the necessary set of foundational Data Science skills to enable them to analyse their data in an efficient and effective manner for the 21st century.

The material covered is fundamental to all areas of Data Science and is

with extensive labs and seminars.

The School will be run on an online basis and participants will be given 7 days a week to complete each topic. Participants will need to allow at least 7 to 8 hours to work through the content of the topic. The content also provides practical exercises and at least one live question and answer session where facilitators will address any concerns the participants may have. Content will be provided as video lectures as well as presentation slides.

Topics: Open Science and Responsible Conduct of Research; Introduction to Unix Shell; Programming for Analysis; Git; Research Data Management; Author Carpentry; Data Visualisation; Information Security; Machine Learning; Computational Infrastructures.

Registration [here](#) - deadline 27 July 2021.

CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science – South Africa

The virtual CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science, hosted by the University of Pretoria, South Africa has been very proud to host 69 participants from 16 countries. This year the school has been entirely online and self-paced, running for 10 weeks, from 3 May to 9 July 2021, covering several themes each week and providing Early Career Researchers with foundational data science skills including technical skills and responsible research practices.

Some positive feedback:

Open Science/Ethics: "The content in this module was very insightful and it leaves the audience with something to think about. It made me realize that, as a researcher, I have a responsibility--I am not only to benefit from open science but also need add to the open science library. I thoroughly enjoyed this module!"

Research Data Management: "Very interesting introduction to the subject of data management and sharing data. I recommend this course for everyone who is interested in the subject as well as students and researchers. The course was well-paced, well-organised, and clearly expressed. A wealth of resources were provided while keeping the instructional videos concise but detailed. Thoroughly enjoyable!"

R: "Thank you for all the effort, I enjoyed the videos, they have been really explanatory. They are comprehensive and detailed. The challenges (some)

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R: "Extremely helpful! I've learned so much about R and it will revolutionise the way I work, especially pipelines and plotting."

Machine Learning: "Content was explained in a very understandable manner even though it was my first time encountering this type of information. I really liked the toy and matching examples being used in explaining everything in a clear practical way."

Neural Networks: "The content was extremely interesting and leaves the audience with the want to know more about neural networks."

Information Security: "The information was really informative. It is extremely important to understand all the implications of handling data. The live session with the demonstration was extremely interesting and useful."

High Performance Computing (HPC): "The course is well explained. Can follow without any prior knowledge. Can be considered as a strong foundation for High Performance Computing field."

More details on the SA School web page: <https://datascienceschools.co.za/>

Alumni Profile

Jacqueline Stephens

I am an epidemiologist based at Flinders University, Australia. My research identifies and addresses healthcare inequity by primarily using data linkage and 'big data' methods to link health and administrative datasets to answer complex questions about health and service usage. My research interests include infectious diseases, child and adolescent health, ear health, and consumer engagement. Following the completion of my PhD in 2017, I was looking for an opportunity to develop my data science skills and to network with other like-minded researchers. The 2018 CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Winter

knowledge of, as well as to consolidate and reinforce my prior learning and experience in those tools and software that I used regularly. Since then, I have continued to network with the Australian CODATA Alumni, as well as connect with members of the international Alumni. I have participated in multiple CODATA activities, have helped organise some of those activities, and am the only Australian representative on the International Science Council's Committee on Data (CODATA) ECR Network committee. The CODATA network keeps me updated on the advances occurring internationally regarding FAIR data stewardship and I thank CODATA and RDA for their leadership.

Alumni Profile

Neema Simon Sumari

I am Neema Simon SUMARI (PhD), a Tanzanian national working as a Lecturer at the Sokoine University of Agriculture (SUA), at the time of writing. I hold an MSc and BSc both in Computer Science, from the Alabama Agriculture and Mechanical University (A&M), US and PhD from Wuhan University, China. I first heard about CODATA in July 2016 when I attended an International Workshop in Beijing in 2016. I was very happy and excited to meet new people there, learning new things and seeing new places. It was the first time I had participated in an International workshop/conference, and the first time to experience this in China where I am now doing my Ph.D. Through that workshop, I made lots of new friends and built a strong network of people in and out of my field of study.

The CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer Schools in Trieste, Italy, in July 2017, and BEIJING 2019 were the best for me. The summer school was amazing, we exchanged academic knowledge as well as building on our existing networks. I wanted to learn and meet new people, ideas and experience different cultures and CODATA and Springer-Nature supported me in attaining these goals. It has been amongst the best experiences in my life. I met a lot of fascinating people from all over the world, expert professors whose lectures were very interesting and helpful to my academic career. I created strong friendships that I hope I will be able to maintain over the next few years if

major key to summer school. I have learned different issues on why data cannot be shared, how can be analyzed, which data has long term value as well as benefits of storing, protecting, sharing, and publishing data among research scientists. It's true that most of the researchers would like their data to be publicly stored and accessible by other researchers, however, this is not easy for researchers who do not have clearly defined ways to do this, or do not know, how to make their data accessible to others. Knowledge of data management plans for the hosting research institutes is required to ensure that researchers can define ways to store their datasets in a publicly accessible way after their experiments are done. Once the research data is stored in a publicly accessible manner, it then needs to be preserved in a format which can be reused by other researchers. In this summer school, the courses that were taught were: Programming-in-R, Cloud Computing, UNIX Shell, ggplot2, Data Visualisation, SQL, Machine Learning, Data Science Profession, Artificial Neural Networks, Research Computational Infrastructure, HOC and HTC, Research Data Management. These courses gave us very good skills and knowledge about Data Science which can help us to facilitate the sharing of data - it was great experience. I now know why Open access and data sharing is important and I will apply and share this knowledge to my professional and Social Media networks.

Last but not the least, was the wonderful arrangement of having helpers to assist us with any logistical problems occurring during the practical sessions and the use of pink sticker was an outstanding style. It was one of the most enjoyable and informative moments of my life.

Thanks to CODATA, RDA, ICTP, and Springer-Nature for your support.

Data Stewardship Training - Belgium

The CODATA-RDA Schools instructors together with FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC Synergy and Ghent University delivered a three day train-the-trainer workshop in June to support the development of data stewardship skills among staff in universities and other research institutions in Belgium. The event gathered 30 participants from the emerging RDM support staff community in the country.

Among the participants, 50% had been in their data steward role for less than 6 months, 18% between 6 and 12 months, and only the remaining 32% had been working as a data steward for longer than a year. Most of the participants (55%)

The aim of the workshop was to introduce participants to the key concepts and drivers for Open Science, RDM and FAIR data, to consider the existing local support service they can leverage and to identify areas where collaboration with peer institutions on support provision will be beneficial. The workshop combined a series of theoretical and practical sessions, where participants were given the opportunity to interact and get to know other colleagues in their professional network and exchange their experience in supporting researchers with RDM. Participants were also introduced to key concepts of pedagogy and were able to put these in practice with a course design and development activity. They also got to evaluate their existing training offer and materials, and to explore other potential open training resources that could help them achieve their training goals. Finally, other sessions allowed participants to reflect on their own role as data stewards and on the status of RDM services in their respective institutions.

The workshop met the expectations and motivation of the participants, who had joined with an interest to learn more about what the role of a data steward entails (“interest in how to be a data steward”, “As a new data steward I wanted to get better at my job”), to learn more about how to provide effective training (“have tips and practical info to organize RDM training”, “to see how others are handling this kind of training”) and to understand how to implement RDM services and advance FAIR data within their organization. When asked about the best aspects of the workshop, participants valued the interactive and hands-on approach of the event (“exercises got us actively engaged in the material”, “combination and practice and theory”), the networking opportunity that was offered (“getting to meet new people”, “sharing experience with other participants”), as well as the discovery of new resources that they can apply to their daily job (“getting to know new tools which can help me to improve as a data steward and improve my training sessions”, “catalogue of training resources”). Participants also identified areas of improvement for future events, namely the lack of time to have deeper discussion or feedback after exercises, taking more time to explain the expected outcome of the practical activities and having the opportunity to introduce each other at the beginning of the event.

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The Botswana Open University Library hosted a Winter School through collaboration with the CODATA-RDA instructors, from 17th to 21st May 2021.

Although our libraries support research activities taking place in our respective institutions, many librarians lack the required data management skills to effectively provide data services. On the other hand, many researchers are also unprepared for and lack sufficient time and skills to handle the requirements of data management. Librarians are therefore better placed to provide support for data management issues such as: data storage, integrity and back-up options. The purpose of the school therefore was to provide better understanding on data stewardship for librarians and application of research data management process for researchers.

The School had a total of 31 participants, dominantly the academic librarians, then research institute librarians as well as researchers across the country. The program of study covered topics in introduction to RDM, responsible and open research and developing and implementing research data policy. The topics provided a bases for discussions and context for implementation and practice in our institutions.

The Winter School Data Stewardship Training was officially launched by Professor Kgomotso N. Moahi, the Deputy Vice Chancellor – Student Services on Monday the 17th May 2021. In her launching remarks Professor Moahi said data stewardship was very critical as it allowed for re-use of data by other researchers, answers new research problems by using existing data, and can also be used to verify research. She encouraged the participants, both librarians and researchers to work together in their future research projects. The ceremony was officially closed by the Deputy Vice Chancellor Professor Frank Youngman who made an observation that in Botswana research activities are not as organised as could be and hopes the three days of training will address some of the gaps. This event therefore was an eye-opener to the local research fraternity.

Testimonials:

When asked how they are going to apply what they have learnt at individual and institutional level? The following are answers from a few anonymous participants.

“I would like to see a functioning research data management framework at my institution”.

“Increase my research efficiency/competence and also share knowledge gained from the training with my colleagues especially on the proper data open policy techniques of research data for future research”

institutional level i plan on developing a framework for the library in delivering RDM services to researchers and also educate others after I have gained depth understanding by reading through the materials on Fairdata forum”.

Instructor Profile

Venkataraman Shanmugasundaram

My name is Venkat and I work for the Digital Curation Centre (DCC). The DCC are based in Edinburgh and Glasgow and I am based in the former... although, as many around the world are also doing, I'm only working remotely. We're a centre of expertise in all things RDM, open research, DMPs, FAIR principles and building the services that are needed to accomplish these. My role in all this is to lead on the training which we deliver to audiences across the world. We primarily focus on research data and your typical audience member at one of our workshops tends to be researchers or the support staff that enable best practice.

Before becoming involved in training in the RDM sphere, I was a biologist, moving from biochemistry and onto developmental biology. It was in the latter in particular that I learnt a lot through practical application about repositories and open research. It was before the days of the FAIR principles but many of the things I did day to day fulfilled the principles. Working for a repository allowed me to get a good understanding of metadata, ontologies, licences and other key aspects of what I am now teaching.

Not long after joining the DCC in 2018, I was enlisted by my then colleague, Sarah Jones, to start helping out with the schools. She was one of the original school's members, and then later stopped contributing due to other work commitments, allowing me to fully take over, and eventually become a co-chair. Our focus is to provide the teaching in the curriculum about RDM, which sits alongside the open and responsible research component, but perhaps more importantly provides a foundation for all the other modules of the schools

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I have been involved with the schools to see some wonderful places and people!

Alumni Webinar Series

Webinar 3: SARS-CoV-2 genomics and data analysis in the UK

Dr Matthew Bashton, Northumbria University

22 July 2021 BST 14:00-15:00

Dr Matthew Bashton is the lead bioinformatician of the COVID-19 Genomics UK Consortium (COG-UK) team at Northumbria University. His talk will describe the software set-up and environment used at Northumbria for delivering their COVID-19 genomics solution, variant, and lineage classification, including pipelines developed as well as other tools in use within COG-UK. The team at Northumbria have successfully sequenced over 16,000 COVID-19 genomes contributing to both genomic surveillance nationally and participating in local outbreak investigations where genomics helped to track the spread of the virus amongst people and inform infection control efforts. Matthew will talk about the challenge of building and maintaining a production software environment, as you use it, in a rapidly developing and constantly evolving landscape.

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